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Parametric analysis for direct vapour generation of organic fluids

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1. Introduction

Solar thermal energy (STE) captures and utilises the Sun's heat for a wide range of applications, setting it apart from solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, which convert sunlight directly into electricity. This technology leverages solar energy to produce heat, which can serve purposes such as water heating, space heating, and electricity generation through thermal processes. STE operates by employing solar collectors that absorb sunlight and convert it into heat. This heat is then transferred to a heat transfer fluid (HTF), commonly water, thermal oil, or molten salts. Among these, thermal oil is the most prevalent in concentrated solar power (CSP) systems due to its effective heat transfer properties [1,2].

In most applications, the heat energy absorbed by the heat transfer fluid (HTF) is converted into a more practical form, typically steam, to drive turbines for electricity generation or provide direct process heat for industries, such as in Solar Heat for Industrial Processes (SHIP). Since the HTF and the working fluid are different substances, heat exchangers facilitate efficient thermal energy transfer to the utility. Direct Vapour Generation (DVG) is an advanced technology that utilises solar energy to produce vapour directly within the solar collector, traditionally using water or steam, known as direct steam generation (DSG). By eliminating the need for conventional heat transfer fluids like oils or molten salts, DVG presents a more efficient and simplified approach to solar thermal energy conversion. The DVG concept has attracted significant attention for its potential to improve efficiency and lower costs in solar power applications [3].

Originally developed for steam Rankine cycles, the DSG concept has now expanded to accommodate the evolution of solar organic Rankine cycles (ORC) [4–7]. This advancement opens the possibility of producing vapour from fluids other than water within solar collectors, as emphasised in Refs. [8–10]. The increasing global demand for Solar Heat for Industrial Processes (SHIP) installations underscores the potential of integrating DSG with heat pumps, leveraging the compatibility of heat transfer fluids (HTFs) used in ORC systems [11,12]. Despite this progress, the existing literature still lacks a comprehensive investigation of flow patterns in receiver tubes for HTFs beyond water.

2. Direct vapour generation concept

Working fluids play a crucial role in solar thermal systems, serving as mediums for energy storage and transfer. In CSP applications, thermal oil has traditionally been the dominant choice, while pressurised water and thermal oils are prevalent in SHIP installations. However, thermal oil faces limitations due to its thermal degradation at temperatures exceeding 400°C, which restricts the maximum operating temperature of these systems. To address this limitation, researchers initially explored the DSG process, which produces steam directly within the solar field [13–15]. Expanding on this concept, the Direct Vapour Generation (DVG) approach has emerged, involving the use of phase-change fluids other than water.

The DVG concept simplifies solar energy utilization by employing a single fluid to serve as both the HTF and the working fluid. In DVG systems, a phase-change fluid circulates through the solar field and undergoes a phase change, typically boiling, to generate energy. The literature on DSG highlights several technical advantages that can be readily applied to DVG. These advantages include the potential to raise the maximum operating temperature of the process, reducing the solar field size and consequently lowering investment costs. Furthermore, DVG systems offer lower operational and maintenance expenses compared to those using thermal oil, which often necessitate regular oil replacement and antifreeze measures when ambient temperatures drop below 14°C.

However, the implementation of DVG introduces significant challenges due to the two-phase flow of liquid and steam within the absorber tubes in the boiling section of the solar field. Addressing these challenges is crucial before advancing to the construction of commercial plants employing this technology. Several key uncertainties must be resolved, including the control of the solar field, ensuring process stability, and managing thermal stresses within the receiver tubes.

2.1 Thermal model

This study adopts a thermohydraulic model originally developed for Direct Steam Generation (DSG) to analyse the solar field. The model utilizes a typical one-dimensional (1D) modelling technique, employing a steady-state energy balance approach on a discretized receiver of a parabolic trough collector (PTC). The energy balance equations incorporate variables such as beam solar irradiation, optical losses, thermal losses from the heat collection element (HCE), and gains in the working fluid. A detailed description of the thermohydraulic model is available in Ref. [16]. Fig. 1 illustrates the heat transfer model in the receiver's cross-section, while Eq. 1 outlines the mathematical framework for modelling the solar field. These equations allow us to predict the thermohydraulic behaviour of the solar field and determine the necessary receiver length to achieve a specific temperature.

Fig. 1. Heat fluxes over the PTC receiver. Adapted from [16]

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{q}'_{12,conv} = \dot{q}'_{23,cond} \\ \dot{q}'_{3,SolAbs} = \dot{q}'_{34,conv} + \dot{q}'_{34,rad} + \dot{q}'_{23,cond} + \dot{q}'_{38,cond} \\ \dot{q}'_{45,cond} = \dot{q}'_{34,conv} + \dot{q}'_{34,rad} \\ \dot{q}'_{45,cond} + \dot{q}'_{5,SolAbs} = \dot{q}'_{56,conv} + \dot{q}'_{57,rad} \\ \dot{q}'_{12,conv} = \frac{\dot{m}}{L_{HCE}} (h_{in} - h_{out}) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Two-phase flow within tubes can manifest in various patterns, each characterized by distinct thermal and hydrodynamic properties. Achieving and maintaining annular flow is essential to ensure optimal heat transfer rates. Therefore, the selection of the flow rate and nominal operating pressure must be carefully considered to promote boiling conditions favourable for annular flow. This study employs the Taitel and Dukler flow map to validate the operational regime and confirm the presence of annular flow [16].

2.2 Fluid selection

Existing literature indicates that Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems and certain heat pumps utilize compatible working fluids [11,12]. For low-to-medium temperature ranges of 100–250°C, PTCs developed by Invenite Power are well-suited for DVG in these systems. To optimize the DVG process, selecting working fluids with critical points between 120 and 250°C is a strategic approach. Among the numerous candidates, four fluids—MM, Pentane, R1233zd(E), and Toluene—have been chosen for evaluation due to their promising applications in ORC and heat pump systems. The phase change process for each fluid will be analysed at 0.3, 0.5, and 0.75 times their critical pressure, under conditions of a Reynolds number of 3×10^5 and a Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) of 650 W/m², which represents the annual average for Agua Prieta, Mexico.

3. Two phase-flow characterization

Direct vapour generation involves the phase transition of the working fluid from liquid to vapour within the solar receiver. The efficiency of this process is critically dependent on effectively managing flow patterns and minimizing pressure drops to ensure stable operation and optimal heat transfer. The vapour quality, representing the proportion of the fluid in the vapour phase, serves as a key parameter in this study. Fig. 2 illustrates the overall performance of the four selected heat transfer fluids (HTFs) on the Taitel and Dukler diagram: MM (red), Pentane (blue), R1233zd(E) (green), and Toluene (purple). The results are categorized by operating pressure, with solid lines indicating 0.3 times the critical pressure, triangular markers representing 0.5 times the critical pressure, and cross markers denoting 0.75 times the critical pressure.

Fig. 2. Two-phase flow for the selected HTF

The Taitel and Dukler diagram in Fig. 2 uses four key dimensionless parameters to capture the balance between forces governing two-phase flow in horizontal tubes. The Froude number (Fr) compares inertial to gravitational forces, indicating whether fluid motion or gravity dominates the flow pattern. The Martinelli parameter (X) is the square root of the ratio of the pressure drop for the liquid flowing alone to that for the vapour, reflecting the relative flow resistances of the phases. The T parameter quantifies the influence of vapour-phase turbulence on the liquid interface by comparing turbulent shear stresses to gravitational forces, thereby indicating the vapour's capacity to disturb the liquid film. Finally, the K parameter measures the effect of interfacial shear—essentially the ratio

of the gas-imposed shear stress to the gravitational stabilizing force—helping to predict when waves on the liquid film will grow and lead to transitions between flow regimes.

3.1 Toluene's behaviour

The behaviour of toluene across the examined pressure levels reveals notable variations in performance metrics. At 0.3 times the critical pressure, toluene exhibited a mass flow rate of 0.9778 kg/s under initial conditions of 12.38 bar and 230.4°C. Despite these settings, a substantial pressure drop over 216 meters caused the flow to cease, achieving a maximum vapour quality of only 0.9186. This outcome indicates that operating at lower fractions of critical pressure for toluene leads to significant pressure losses, hindering the fluid's complete phase transition to vapour.

In contrast, at 0.5 and 0.75 times the critical pressure, toluene reached full vapour quality (quality of 1) at shorter pipeline lengths of 136 meters and 72 meters, respectively, with lower pressure drops of 1.936 bar and 0.3758 bar. These findings highlight that higher operating pressures enhance phase transition efficiency, minimize pressure drops, and improve the system's performance and sustainability. These results align with theoretical expectations that higher pressures improve phase transition efficiency and reduce associated losses.

3.2 MM's behaviour

MM's performance further confirms the pressure dependence observed in toluene. At 0.3 times the critical pressure, with initial conditions of 5.818 bar and 174°C and a mass flow rate of 0.8357 kg/s, MM experienced a substantial pressure drop of 4.382 bar over 108 meters, yet successfully reached complete vapour quality. This result highlights MM's robustness in achieving phase change despite significant pressure drops.

As the pressure increased to 0.5 and 0.75 times the critical pressure, the required lengths to achieve full vapour quality reduced to 60 meters and 28 meters, respectively, with corresponding pressure drops of 0.6501 bar and 0.1113 bar. The decrease in pressure drop and pipeline length necessary for full boiling at higher pressures demonstrates enhanced efficiency, suggesting that MM is a viable candidate for DVG systems where moderate pressure losses are acceptable.

3.3 R1233zd(E)'s behaviour

The refrigerant demonstrated a similar trend, with notable improvements in performance at elevated pressures. At 0.3 times the critical pressure, the refrigerant achieved complete vapour quality despite a significant pressure drop of 7.124 bar over 152 meters, highlighting the operational challenges at lower pressures.

When the pressure increased to 0.5 and 0.75 times the critical pressure, the refrigerant's performance enhanced substantially, achieving full boiling at reduced pipeline lengths of 92 meters and 28 meters, respectively, with lower pressure drops of 1.337 bar and 0.1522 bar. These findings indicate that refrigerants can effectively leverage higher pressures to optimize phase transition processes, making them well-suited for applications requiring efficient heat transfer with manageable pressure losses.

3.4 Pentane's behaviour

The refrigerant demonstrated a similar trend, with notable improvements in performance at elevated pressures. At 0.3 times the critical pressure, the refrigerant achieved complete vapour quality despite a significant pressure drop of 7.124 bar over 152 meters, highlighting the operational challenges at lower pressures.

When the pressure increased to 0.5 and 0.75 times the critical pressure, the refrigerant's performance enhanced substantially, achieving full boiling at reduced pipeline lengths of 92 meters and 28 meters, respectively, with lower pressure drops of 1.337 bar and 0.1522 bar. These findings indicate that refrigerants can effectively leverage higher pressures to optimize phase transition processes, making them well-suited for applications requiring efficient heat transfer with manageable pressure losses.

3.5 HTF comparison

The comparative analysis of the four fluids reveals a consistent trend: increasing the fraction of the critical pressure generally results in reduced pressure drops and shorter pipeline lengths required to achieve full vapour quality. This trend is particularly pronounced in fluids such as toluene and refrigerant, where higher pressures lead to significant efficiency enhancements.

However, the degree of these improvements varies among the fluids. Toluene and MM exhibit considerable resilience in reaching complete boiling even at lower pressures, whereas the refrigerant and pentane show more pronounced efficiency gains at higher pressures. These findings suggest that the implementation of refrigerant and pentane in direct vapour generation (DVG) systems should carefully balance pressure levels and system design to optimize overall efficiency.

4. Conclusions

This study aimed to investigate the Direct Vapour Generation (DVG) concept in solar thermal systems by analysing the performance of four different heat transfer fluids—Toluene, MM, R1233zd(E), and Pentane—under various operating conditions. The research focused on optimizing the annular flow pattern within receiver tubes to minimize dry-out risks and enhance heat transfer efficiency. A detailed experimental approach was employed, examining fluid behaviour across different pressures to assess their suitability for DVG applications.

We demonstrated that the selection of appropriate fluids and operating conditions significantly influences the efficiency and performance of DVG systems. The study reveals that Toluene and MM are effective for applications where moderate pressure losses are acceptable, while R1233zd(E) and Pentane excel in higher-pressure systems, minimizing pressure drops and maximizing

heat transfer coefficients. However, Toluene's limited ability to generate saturated steam at lower pressures poses constraints on its use in specific scenarios.

Despite these constraints, the research contributes valuable insights into two-phase flow dynamics within DVG systems, offering a basis for optimizing such systems in applications like Organic Rankine Cycles (ORC) and high-temperature heat pumps. The findings align with and extend previous research by highlighting the critical role of pressure management in enhancing system efficiency, thus advancing our understanding of solar thermal technology.

Future investigations should consider the integration of these fluids into more comprehensive solar thermal systems, accounting for dynamic environmental conditions and operational transients. Exploring hybrid systems capable of dynamically adjusting pressures and flow rates could yield further advancements in DVG technology. Addressing these questions will continue to expand the applicability and efficiency of solar thermal systems, promoting their role in sustainable energy solutions.

Ultimately, this study broadens the scope of DVG research by incorporating alternative working fluids, thereby paving the way for more adaptable and resilient solar thermal technologies with diverse industrial applications.

5. References

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